

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 4.1 to AD4.1 – Blood Sampling Questionnaire for Adults (18 – 39 years)

WP 4

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other program participants (including the Commission Services)

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CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
Version 1	2023-06-22	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr; Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	
Version 2	2023-07-11	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr; Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	Small adaptations after external review of AD4.1
Version 3	2023-09-18	Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	Small adaptations after GS partners' review of the questionnaires

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B.01: Question for fieldworker about blood sample collection

Q130: Has the blood sample been taken?

Yes

No

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q130.1: Please indicate the reason for missing submission of the blood sample

Unsuccessful puncture

No consent

Sampling was spontaneously refused

Other reason

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q130.1.1: Other reason, that being _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q131: When was the blood sample obtained? **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q131.1: On **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q131.1.1: Day _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q131.1.2: Month _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q131.1.3: Year _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q131.2: At **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q131.2.1: Hour _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q131.2.2: Minute _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q133: What total amount was sampled? _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q133.1: Please specify which tubes **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q133.1.1: Plastic serum vacutainer 4ml

Yes

No

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q133.1.2: Glass serum vacutainer 5ml

Yes

No

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q133.1.3: Edta vacutainer 6ml

Yes

No

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q134: If the gross volume was taken in sub-samples: how many sub-samples were taken? **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q134.1: Small tubes **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q134.1.1: Amount _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q134.1.2: Volume taken in each sub-sample _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q134.2: Large tubes **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q134.2.1: Amount _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q134.2.2: Volume taken in each sub-sample _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q135: Is there a sampling label on the container?

Yes

No

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q136: Is there a label with the correct participant id on the container?

Yes

No

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q137: Were there any peculiarities with the sample or participant's answers?

No

Yes

Refused to provide sample

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q137.1: Which ones? _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

I.00: Questionnaire information

Q093: Id (participant) _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q094: Id (interviewer) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q095: Date of the interview **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q095.1: Day _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q095.2: Month _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q095.3: Year _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q098: Interview place / interview platform _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

B.02: Question for participant about blood sample collection

Q132: When was your last meal before blood sample collection? **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.1: On **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.1.1: Day _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.1.2: Month _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.1.3: Year _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.2: At **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.2.1: Hour _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q132.2.2: Minute _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

UB.03: Recent exposure

Q138: Before providing the sample, when did you last eat any food belonging to the following food groups?

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.1: White fish (e.G. Hake, snapper, sea bream, cod, haddock, grouper, halibut, tilapia, bass)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.2: Small oily fish (e.G. Anchovy, sardines, salmon)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

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Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.3: Big oily fish (e.G. Sword fish, tuna, school shark)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.4: Other seafood (e.G. Octopus, squid, shrimps, scampi)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.5: Meat (e.G. White and red meat, game, offal)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.6: Snails

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.7: Rice

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.8: Other cereals (e.G. Bread, crackers, grains, pasta)

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.9: Algae/seaweeds

Not at all

Less than 12 hours ago

Between 12 and 24 hours ago

Between 24 and 48 hours ago

Between 48 and 72 hours ago

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(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.10: Mushrooms

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.11: Vegetables (e.G. Potatoes, leafy vegetables)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.12: Fruits (e.G. Oranges, grapes, apples)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.13: Dairy products (e.G. Butter, milk, cheese)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.14: Fats (animal, e.G. Lard and vegetal, e.G. Olive or sunflower oil)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.15: Potato chips (packaged)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.16: Microwave popcorn (cooked in bags)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

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Q138.18: Peanuts

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.19: Chewing gum

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.20: Smoked food (e.G. Ham, smoked pork, smoked cheese, frankfurters)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q138.21: Canned food

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.22: Fast food

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q138.23: Ready meals (in plastic packaging)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q139: When did you last take dietary supplements (algae, spirulina, vitamins, minerals, omega-3 fatty acids etc...) during the past 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- Not at all
- Less than 5 hours ago
- Between 5 and 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q139.1: If yes, please specify supplement _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q140: Before providing the sample, when did you last drink any beverages belonging to the following list?

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(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q140.1: Barley coffee

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours ago
- Between 12 and 24 hours ago
- Between 24 and 48 hours ago
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q140.3: Whole milk

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q140.4: Vegetable/fruit juice (hand-made)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q140.5: Vegetable/fruit juice (processed)

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q140.6: Beer

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q140.7: Red wine

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q140.8: Japanese rice wine 'sake'

- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q140.9: Tea or any other drink prepared in metal recipient (e.G. Arabic teapot)

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- Not at all
- Less than 12 hours
- Between 12 and 24 hours
- Between 24 and 48 hours
- Between 48 and 72 hours ago

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q141: Have you been exposed to tobacco smoke during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- No
- Yes, i have smoked
- Yes, i have been exposed to second hand smoke (passive smoking)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q141.1: How many cigarettes and other smoking products did you smoke during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- 1-5
- 6-10
- 11 or more
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q141.2: How long have you been exposed to secondhand smoking during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- Less than an hour
- More than 1 hour
- More than 4 hours
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q142: Have you been exposed to electronic cigarettes vapors during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- No
- Yes, i have vaped
- Yes, i have been exposed to secondhand vape smoke

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q142.1: How many puffs of e-cigarettes did you take during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- 1-5
- 6-10
- 11 or more
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q142.2: How long have you been exposed to secondhand vape smoke during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- Less than an hour
- More than 1 hour
- More than 4 hours
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q143: Have you used any smokeless tobacco products such as snuff/snus, dip, or chewing tobacco during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- No
- Yes

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q143.1: How many loadings did you take during the 24 hrs prior to sampling?

- 1-2
- 3-5
- 6 or more
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

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Q144: Did you take any medicines during the past 24 hrs prior to sampling?

No

Yes

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q144.1: If yes, please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q145: During the past 24 hrs prior to sampling, did you undergo one or more of the following medical treatments?

Choose from the following options: **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q145.1: Intravenous (iv) infusion **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q145.2: Donated blood **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q145.3: Dialysis **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q145.4: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**